

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

DNA Barcoding of Selected Green Macroalgae Using 18S rDNA Diversity

Kavitha Venkatachalam^{1*}, Lakshmi Sundaram¹, Sangeetha Anand¹,
Sheeja Prasad¹

¹ PG Department of Plant Biology and Plant Biotechnology, Shrimathi Devkunvar Nanalal, Bhatt Vaishnav College for Women (Autonomous), Chrompet, Chennai-600 044, Tamil Nadu, India

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* **Corresponding author.**

kavichiqli@gmail.com

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Abstract

Objectives: To develop DNA barcodes for green algae to enable precise, rapid identification; this work intends to address challenges due to limited or obscure morphological traits in many species. **Method:** Analyzed 18S rDNA sequences from *Chaetomorpha*, *Enteromorpha* and *Ulva* specimens. PCR amplified fragments (1673, 1648, and 1652 bp) were sequenced. Evaluated the efficacy of a single 18S rDNA locus as a DNA barcode marker. Compared sequences to assess species delineation and validate taxonomic classifications. **Findings:** 18S rDNA sequence analysis identified three species and revealed that *Enteromorpha* and *Ulva* are not distinct genera, aligning with modern molecular taxonomic revisions. This supports DNA barcoding as a reliable tool for species-level identification in Chlorophyceae, providing novel molecular evidence that enhances existing taxonomic and biodiversity research by clarifying evolutionary relationships. **Novelty:** Validated DNA barcoding as a precise, efficient tool for green algae taxonomy, resolving the taxonomic ambiguity between *Enteromorpha* and *Ulva*.

Keywords: Chlorophyceae; DNA barcoding; 18S rDNA; MEGA; phylogenetic analysis

1 Introduction

Accurate species identification is fundamental to biodiversity assessment, ecological monitoring, and evolutionary studies. Traditional taxonomy, established through morphological and anatomical criteria, has long provided the basis for classifying living organisms. However, this approach is increasingly inadequate for taxa with simple body plans and high phenotypic plasticity. Macroalgae are macroscopic, aquatic, photosynthetic organisms distributed among three major phyla—Ochrophyta, Rhodophyta, and Chlorophyta—and constitute a substantial proportion of coastal primary production⁽¹⁾. Among these, green macroalgae pose persistent taxonomic difficulties due to reduced morphological complexity, convergent evolution, environmentally driven variability, and limited diagnostic characters, often leading to misidentification and unresolved species boundaries^{(1), (2)}.

To address these limitations, molecular approaches—particularly DNA barcoding—have been introduced as complementary tools for species identification. DNA

barcoding relies on short, standardized DNA sequences that show low intraspecific variation but sufficient interspecific divergence, enabling rapid and reproducible taxonomic assignment⁽³⁾. Early molecular studies using ribosomal and plastid markers demonstrated the potential of sequence-based methods in resolving algal taxonomy and evolutionary relationships⁽⁴⁾,⁽⁵⁾,⁽⁶⁾. In green algae, nuclear 18S rDNA has emerged as a widely used barcode marker due to its conserved structure, universal primers, and utility in phylogenetic inference across taxonomic levels, often supplemented by ITS regions for finer species resolution⁽⁷⁾.

Despite these advances, significant gaps remain in the molecular taxonomy of green macroalgae. First, many morphologically identified taxa lack validated barcode sequences in public reference databases, limiting the reliability of molecular identifications. Second, most DNA barcoding studies in algae emphasize phylogenetic reconstruction rather than rigorous species delimitation, often relying on arbitrary genetic distance thresholds that may not adequately reflect species boundaries in morphologically plastic lineages, a limitation previously discussed in microbial taxonomy studies⁽⁸⁾. Third, molecular data are frequently generated without integration with classical taxonomic observations, resulting in fragmented and incomplete species assessments. Consequently, cryptic diversity remains underestimated, and taxonomic inconsistencies persist within green macroalgal groups.

Addressing these gaps requires systematic application of DNA barcoding markers to morphologically characterized green macroalgae, coupled with robust sequence analysis and comparison against curated databases. Such an integrated approach is essential for resolving taxonomic ambiguities, improving species delimitation, and strengthening molecular reference libraries, thereby advancing our understanding of green macroalgal diversity and systematics. In this study, we aimed to apply 18S rDNA-based DNA barcoding to resolve the taxonomic uncertainty between *Enteromorpha* and *Ulva* using samples collected from the coast of Tamil Nadu, India.

2 Methodology

2.1 Collection of Samples

Three different species of green macroalgae (Chlorophyceae) were collected from two distinct localities (Pulicat Lake and Kovalong Coast) in Tamil Naduduring January–June 2015. They were identified as *Ulva* sp., *Chaetomorpha* sp., and *Enteromorpha* sp. *Enteromorpha* sp. was collected from Pulicat Lake (Figure 1A), while *Chaetomorpha* sp. and *Ulva* sp. were collected from Kovalong Coast (Figure 1B). The collected specimens are shown in Figure 2 (A–C). The fresh specimens were placed in separate plastic bags without water and transported to the laboratory in an icebox. Samples were stored at -20°C until DNA extraction. The voucher specimens were deposited at the herbarium of the Department of Plant Biology and Plant Biotechnology, SDNB Vaishnav College for Women, Chromepet and Chennai-600 044.

Fig 1. Collection sites of green macroalgae from Tamil Nadu, India. (A) Pulicat Lake – collection site of *Enteromorpha* sp. (B) Kovalong Coast – collection site of *Chaetomorpha* sp. and *Ulva* sp.

2.2 Genomic DNA Isolation

Fresh algal tissue (approximately 100 mg) was thoroughly washed with sterile distilled water to remove surface contaminants and blotted dry. The tissue was finely homogenized using a sterile mortar and pestle. Genomic DNA was extracted using the High Pure PCR Template Preparation Kit (Roche, Germany) according to the manufacturer's protocol. DNA was eluted in 50 μL of elution buffer. The quality and integrity of the extracted DNA were assessed using 1% agarose gel electrophoresis.

Fig 2. Morphological features of collected green macroalgae. (A) *Enteromorpha sp.* (tubular thallus), (B) *Chaetomorpha sp.* (filamentous thallus), (C) *Ulva sp.* (sheet-like thallus).

2.3 PCR Amplification

The 18S rDNA region was amplified using published universal primers: forward primer SSU1 (5′-TGGTTGATCCTGCCAGTA-3′) and reverse primer SSU2 (5′-TGATCCTTCCGCAGGTTTCAC-3′) (Shoup and Lewis, 2003). PCR amplification was performed in a 25 μ L reaction mixture containing 12.5 μ L of 2 \times PCR Master Mix, 1 μ L each of forward and reverse primers (10 pmol; final concentration 0.4 μ M), 2 μ L of template DNA (20–50 ng), and nuclease-free water to complete the final volume. The thermal cycling conditions were as follows: initial denaturation at 94°C for 5 min; 35 cycles of denaturation at 94°C for 45 s, annealing at 55°C for 45 s, and extension at 72°C for 1 min; followed by a final extension at 72°C for 5 min. The amplified products were stored at –20°C until further analysis.

2.4 Analysis of PCR Products by Gel Electrophoresis

The amplified products were checked by 1.0% agarose gel electrophoresis in 1 \times TAE buffer at 80–100 V for approximately 45 min. Fragments of 18S rDNA region were cut from the gel and purified.

2.5 Sequencing Analysis

The 18S rDNA region from three samples was sequenced using the Sanger method (Di-deoxynucleotide chain termination). High-quality nucleotide sequences of the target 18S rDNA region were obtained for all samples.

2.6 Data Analysis

Individual sequences obtained in this study were compared with accessions in the National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) using BLAST analysis. Additional sequences were retrieved from GenBank in order to compare interspecific and intraspecific nucleotide divergences and to produce the phylogeny of *Chaetomorpha*, *Enteromorpha*, and *Ulva* using the currently available data. The best-fit nucleotide substitution model was determined using MEGA version 6⁽⁹⁾.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Molecular Analysis

Amplification and sequencing of the nuclear 18S rDNA locus yielded high-quality sequences ranging from 1648 to 1673 bp across the three taxa. The assembled sequence lengths were 1673 bp for *Chaetomorpha sp.*, 1648 bp for *Enteromorpha sp.*, and 1652 bp for *Ulva sp.* BLAST analysis against the NCBI database confirmed their taxonomic affiliation, showing \geq 99% similarity with previously deposited sequences.

Pairwise comparisons revealed approximately 99% sequence identity between *Enteromorpha* and *Ulva*, indicating minimal nucleotide divergence between these taxa. In contrast, greater divergence was observed between the *Ulva*–*Enteromorpha* cluster and *Chaetomorpha*, supporting intergeneric differentiation.

The newly generated sequences were deposited in GenBank under accession numbers KT943567 (*Chaetomorpha sp.*), KT943568 (*Enteromorpha sp.*), and KT943569 (*Ulva sp.*), thereby enriching molecular reference data for Indian green macroalgae. The details of the species analyzed along with their corresponding GenBank accession numbers are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. List of species used in this study and GenBank accession number for 18S rDNA

Taxon	18S rDNA
<i>Ulva intestinalis</i>	AF189077
<i>Ulva californica</i>	AY303586
<i>Ulva curvata</i>	AF189078
<i>Ulva linza</i>	AB425962
<i>Ulva prolifera</i>	HQ850569
<i>Ulva flexuosa</i>	AB425963
<i>Ulva sp</i>[<i>Enteromorpha sp</i>]	KT943568
<i>Ulva pertusa</i>	AB425961
<i>Ulva shanxiensis</i> voucher SAS:06035	KJ617035
<i>Ulva lactuca</i>	AB425960
<i>Ulva compressa</i>	AB425967
<i>Ulva rigida</i>	AJ005414
<i>Ulva fasciata</i>	AB425964
<i>Ulva fasciata</i>	KT943569
<i>Cladophora albida</i>	AB665585
<i>Cladophora vagabunda</i> voucher PEUFR:CON	FJ715648
<i>Cladophora opaca</i>	AB665580
<i>Cladophora oligocladoidea</i>	AB665581
<i>Chaetomorpha moniligera</i>	AB062703
<i>Chaetomorpha crassa</i>	AB062701
<i>Rhizoclonium grande</i>	AB062714
<i>Chaetomorpha</i>	KT943567
<i>Chaetomorpha antennina</i>	AB062700

3.2 Genomic DNA and PCR Amplification

High-quality genomic DNA was successfully extracted from all samples, as indicated by distinct high-molecular-weight bands on 1% agarose gel electrophoresis (Figure 3 and 4). PCR amplification using universal SSU1 and SSU2 primers generated clear amplicons of approximately 1700 bp in all taxa (Figure 4), consistent with previously reported sizes for chlorophyte 18S rDNA sequences.

The uniform amplification across morphologically distinct taxa demonstrates the suitability of universal ribosomal primers for molecular identification of green macroalgae.

3.3 Sequence Characteristics and GenBank Submission

Multiple sequence alignment with 21 reference sequences retrieved from GenBank revealed low intraspecific variation within the *Ulva-Enteromorpha* cluster (0.2–1% divergence), whereas intergeneric divergence between this cluster and *Chaetomorpha* was comparatively higher. The conserved nature of the 18S rDNA locus resulted in short branch lengths among closely related *Ulva* taxa, reflecting limited nucleotide divergence.

The deposition of newly generated sequences from Tamil Nadu contributes region-specific molecular data to global databases, addressing the underrepresentation of tropical Indian macroalgae highlighted in previous biodiversity assessments⁽¹⁾.

3.4 Phylogenetic Analyses

Phylogenetic relationships were inferred using Neighbor-Joining (NJ)⁽¹⁰⁾, Maximum Likelihood (ML), and Minimum Evolution (ME)⁽¹¹⁾ methods implemented in MEGA6⁽⁹⁾. The best-fit nucleotide substitution model was selected based on the Bayesian Information Criterion, and nodal support was evaluated using 1000 bootstrap replicates following Felsenstein⁽¹²⁾.

Fig 3. Agarose Gel (1%) showing Lambda DNA/Hind III Digest Marker & Genomic DNA Lane 1 – Lambda DNA/Hind III Digest Marker
 Lane 2 – Genomic DNA of **1K** (*Chaetomorpha* sp)
 Lane 3 – Genomic DNA of **2K** (*Enteromorpha* sp)
 Lane 4 – Genomic DNA of **3K** (*Ulva* sp)

All three analytical approaches produced congruent topologies. In each reconstruction, *Enteromorpha* clustered firmly within the *Ulva* clade with strong bootstrap support (>95%), confirming the absence of a distinct monophyletic lineage. Within the *Ulva* clade, *Ulva fasciata* grouped closely with *U. rigida*, forming well-supported sister taxa. The short branch lengths observed within this cluster reflect low genetic divergence among closely related taxa.

In contrast, *Chaetomorpha* formed a clearly distinct and well-supported clade, separated from representatives of Ulvales. As all three analytical approaches produced congruent topologies, the Maximum Likelihood, Neighbor-Joining, and Minimum Evolution trees are presented in the main manuscript (Figures 5–7), whereas expanded and supplementary versions of these reconstructions (Figures 5A–5B, 6A–6B and 7A–7B) are provided in the Supplementary Material.

The present study applied 18S rDNA-based DNA barcoding to resolve taxonomic relationships among selected green macroalgae from Tamil Nadu. The high sequence similarity (99%) and consistent phylogenetic clustering of *Enteromorpha* within the *Ulva* clade across NJ, ML, and ME analyses strongly support the view that these taxa are not genetically distinct at the genus level.

3.5 Discussion

These findings corroborate earlier molecular studies demonstrating that tubular *Enteromorpha* morphotypes are phylogenetically nested within sheet-like *Ulva* lineages, supporting their taxonomic consolidation^{(13), (14)}. Earlier molecular analyses have shown that the morphological distinction between *Ulva* and *Enteromorpha* lacks phylogenetic support⁽¹⁵⁾. The present results independently corroborate this taxonomic consolidation.

The repeated recovery of this clustering pattern across different geographic regions suggests that morphological differentiation in Ulvales reflects phenotypic plasticity rather than deep genetic divergence. Environmental factors such as salinity gradients, nutrient availability, hydrodynamic conditions, and bacterial associations have been shown to influence thallus morphology and developmental patterns in *Ulva* species^{(16), (17)}. Such environmentally induced plasticity likely contributed to historical misclassification based solely on thallus architecture.

PCR Product

Fig 4. Agarose Gel (1%) showing 1 Kb DNA ladder and PCR Product Lane 1 – 1 Kb DNA Ladder
 Lane 2 – PCR product of 1K (*Chaetomorpha* sp)
 Lane 3 – PCR product of 2K (*Enteromorpha* sp)
 Lane 4 – PCR product of 3K (*Ulva* sp)

Fig 5. Maximum Likelihood Phylogenetic Tree Constructed from 18S rDNA Sequences

Fig 6. Neighbor-Joining Phylogenetic Tree Constructed from 18S rDNA Sequences.

Fig 7. Minimum Evolution Phylogenetic Tree Constructed from 18S rDNA Sequences.

The conserved nature of the 18S rDNA locus explains the minimal divergence observed within the *Ulva-Enteromorpha* assemblage. While this marker is effective for resolving intergeneric and higher-level relationships, its relatively slow evolutionary rate limits its discriminatory power among closely related species. Similar limitations of conserved ribosomal markers in resolving closely related taxa have been discussed previously in molecular taxonomy studies⁽⁸⁾. Future investigations incorporating faster-evolving regions such as ITS or plastid genes (e.g., *rbcl*) may provide enhanced resolution for species-level delimitation within Ulvales.

The distinct and well-supported clustering of *Chaetomorpha* confirms its independent evolutionary position within Chlorophyceae, consistent with earlier phylogenetic analyses⁽¹⁵⁾,⁽¹⁸⁾. The congruence among multiple phylogenetic reconstruction methods strengthens confidence in the robustness of the inferred relationships.

By generating and depositing new 18S rDNA sequences from Indian coastal ecosystems, this study contributes valuable molecular data to global reference libraries and reinforces the importance of integrating molecular and morphological approaches in algal taxonomy. Such integration is essential for accurate biodiversity assessment, ecological monitoring, and understanding evolutionary diversification within green macroalgae.

4 Conclusion

This study successfully applied 18S rDNA-based DNA barcoding to assess the taxonomic relationships among selected green macroalgae from the coastal regions of Tamil Nadu, India. High-quality sequences ranging from 1648 to 1673 bp were generated and deposited in GenBank (KT943567–KT943569), contributing valuable molecular data from an underrepresented geographic region.

Phylogenetic analyses using Neighbor-Joining, Maximum Likelihood, and Minimum Evolution methods produced congruent topologies, consistently clustering *Enteromorpha* within the *Ulva* clade with strong bootstrap support (>95%). The observed 99% sequence similarity and minimal nucleotide divergence (0.2–1%) between these taxa provide molecular evidence supporting their taxonomic consolidation, consistent with previous global molecular studies.

The distinct and well-supported separation of *Chaetomorpha* further validates the utility of 18S rDNA for resolving intergeneric relationships within Chlorophyceae. However, the conserved nature of the 18S locus limits its discriminatory power among closely related *Ulva* species, highlighting the need for complementary markers such as ITS or plastid genes in future studies.

Overall, this study reinforces the importance of integrating molecular barcoding approaches with traditional morphological taxonomy to resolve taxonomic ambiguities in morphologically plastic algal groups. The generation of region-specific molecular data strengthens global reference libraries and provides a foundation for future biodiversity monitoring and phylogenetic investigations of Indian green macroalgae.

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6 Disclosure Statement

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest associated with this manuscript.

7 Author Contributions

Kavitha conceptualized the study and prepared the original draft of the manuscript. All authors contributed to data interpretation, critical revision of the manuscript, and approved the final version for publication.

8 Data Availability Statement

The data generated and analyzed in this study are included within the article. The 18S rDNA sequences generated in this study have been deposited in GenBank under accession numbers KT943567–KT943569”.

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